

**NESCent Awards
Listed by Year and Round
Years 1-5**

**Year 1: 12/01/04 - 11/30/05
Round 1 - May 2005**

Postdoctoral Fellows

- Kirsten Fisher, Univ of California - Berkeley
The phylogenomics of desiccation tolerance in the land plants
- Joshua Granek, Johns Hopkins Univ
Comparative genomic studies of the sequences responsible for the regulation of gene expression
- Einat Hazkani-Covo, Tel-Aviv Univ
Numt variation in metazoan genomes: gain, loss, duplication and possible function
- Joe Hereford, Florida St Univ - Tallahassee
Adaptive divergence between natural populations
- David Kidd, Univ of St Andrews, UK
Phylogeographical information science: linking phylogenies and earth history
- Samantha Price, University of Virginia
Cetartiodactyl evolution: understanding the evolutionary transition from the terrestrial to the aquatic biome
- Amy Zanne, Masaryk Univ, Brno, Czech Rep
Hydraulic efficiency and safety: Do tradeoffs have an evolutionary basis in the rosids?
- Derrick Zwickl, Univ of Texas, Austin
Implementation of a wide range of codon and amino acid models in Bayesian phylogenetic software

Sabbatical Scholars

- John Clamp, North Carolina Central Univ
 - 1) Attracting minority graduate applicants into careers in evolutionary biology and
 - 2) develop research in molecular systematics
- Quentin Cronk, University of British Columbia, Vancouver
Creating an evolutionary dataspace for plants: allowing phylogenetic, morphological and gene ontologies to collide gracefully

- Paul Lewis, University of Connecticut
Incorporation of all maximum likelihood phylogenetic analyses currently performed by PAUP*4b10 into Phycas
- Jijun Tang, Univ of South Carolina
1) Software integration and 2) permutation sampling for genomic distance
- Adam Eyre-Walker, Univ of Sussex, UK
1) Distribution of fitness effects of new mutations and 2) the rate of adaptive evolution
- Owen McMillan, Univ of Puerto Rico - Rio Pedras
Relational evolutionary database for *Heliconius* butterflies

Triangle Visiting Scholars (no NESCent funding)

- Patricia Gensel, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Evolutionary relationships of Devonian age fossil plants
- Spencer Muse, North Carolina St Univ
Analysis of genetic data
- Todd Vision, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Genome evolution and architecture of complex traits, with a focus on flowering plants
- Greg Wray, Duke Univ
Evolution of development and the molecular evolution of transcriptional regulation

Visiting Scholars

- Louise Roth, Duke University
Squirrels as Models in Macroevolution; Scaling (not funded)
- Jijun Tang, Univ of South Carolina
1) Software Integration and 2) Permutation Sampling for Genomic Distance
- Rytas Vilgalys, Duke Univ
Phylogenetic Systematics and Molecular Evolution in Fungi (not funded)

Catalysis Groups

- Richard Glor, Jonathan Losos, Robert Ricklefs; Univ of California, Washington Univ, Univ of Missouri - St. Louis
Biological diversification on the West Indian Archipelago
- Stephen Proulx, Daniel Promislow, Matthew Hahn; Univ of Oregon, Univ of Georgia, Indiana Univ
Integrated studies of genetic networks: A new evolutionary synthesis

- Daniel Schmitt, Duke Univ
Behavioral reconstruction in paleoanthropology

Working Groups

- Michael Donoghue, Paul Manos; Yale Univ, Duke Univ
Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere
- Susan Kaliz, Mark Johnston; Univ of Pittsburgh, Dalhousie Univ
Understanding the paradox of mixed mating in flowering plants
- Paula Mabee, Monte Westerfield; Univ of South Dakota, Univ of Oregon
Towards an integrated database for fish evolution

Year 2 - 12/1/05 - 11/30/06

Round 2 - March 2006

Postdoctoral Fellows

- Gordon Burleigh, Univ California - Davis
A phylogenetic database for comparative biology in land plants
- Ganeshkumar Ganapathy, Univ Texas - Austin
New DCM methods for ML, and pattern identification in biogeography
- Jason Hoeksema, Univ of California - Santa Cruz
What is the relative importance of biotic vs. abiotic local adaptation?
- Samantha Hopkins, Univ of California - Berkeley
The evolution of mammalian fossoriality: Causes and consequences
- Lauren W. McCall, Univ of Cambridge
Building a framework for the study of cultural evolution
- Brian Sidlauskas, Univ of Chicago
Understanding parallel morphological diversification in sister fish faunas

Sabbatical Scholars

- Douglas Eernisse, California St Univ - Fullerton
Chiton phylogeny and comparative phylogeography
- Joseph Fail, Jr., Johnson C. Smith Univ
Designing and teaching an evolution curriculum for elementary students
- Sarah Otto, Univ of British Columbia
A community approach to evolutionary theory

- Michael Whitlock, Univ of British Columbia
Evolution in a spatial context: A synthesis of theory and review

Triangle Visiting Scholars (no NESCent funding)

- Maria Servedio, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Analysis of factors that determine the occurrence of speciation and reinforcement
- John Willis, Duke Univ
Evolutionary Genomics and Bioinformatics of *Mimulus*, a Developing model system for studies of plant adaptation and speciation

Visiting Scholars

- Clara B. Jones, Fayetteville State Univ
Comparative Sociobiology and Behavioral Ecology (not funded)
- Martin Ramirez, Argentina Natural Science Museum
Connecting Best Practices Experiences and User Interface Development for Morphological Databases

Catalysis Meetings

- Raju Govindaraju, Stephen Stearns, Peter Byers; Boston Univ School of Medicine, Yale Univ, Univ of Washington
Evolution in contemporary human populations: Medical, genetic and behavioral implications
- Kimberly Hughes, Detlef Weigel, Felix Breden; Univ of Illinois, Max Planck Institute, Simon Fraser University
Developing new model systems for evolutionary genomics using Poeciliid fishes
- Thomas Kocher, Univ of New Hampshire
Genomic approaches to the study of adaptive radiation
- Anne Yoder, Claire Kremen; Duke Univ, Univ of California - Berkeley
Patterns of biodiversity in Madagascar

Working Groups

- John R. Jungck, Anton E. Weisstein; BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium, Beloit College, Truman State University
Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in AcTION
- Jim Leebens-Mack, Eric Brenner; Penn St Univ, New York Botanical Garden
The plant evogenomics working group: Advancing comparative functional genomics
- Mohamed Noor, Maria Servedio; Duke Univ, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Proposal to develop a novel journal concept for evolutionary meta-analyses

- Todd Oakley, Univ of California - Santa Barbara
Fossil and molecular estimates of divergence times for the tree of life: Database and synthesis

Triangle Working Group

- Julia Clarke, Nathalie Nagalingum, Brian Wiegmann; North Carolina State Univ, Duke Univ, North Carolina State Univ
Clockwork: Redefining interfaces for molecular biology and paleontology

Round 3 - September 2006

Catalysis Meetings

- Fred Gould, Steven Sinkins, Daniel Hartl; North Carolina State Univ, Oxford Univ, Harvard Univ
Selfish DNA and the genetic control of vector-borne diseases
- Roy Plotnick, Univ of Illinois at Chicago
Origins and evolution of chemoreception

Working Groups

- Casey Bergman, Martin Kreitman, Manolis Dermitzakis; Univ of Manchester, Univ of Chicago, The Wellcome Trust Sanger Inst, UK
Synthesizing computational resources for Cis-regulatory molecular evolution.
- Joel Cracraft, Mark Siddall; American Museum of Natural History
Developing an integrative algorithmic method for historical biogeography
- Paul Magwene, David Houle; Duke Univ, Florida State Univ
Modeling variation in gene networks
- Jonathan Payne, Jennifer Stempien, Michal Kowalewski; Stanford Univ, Virginia Polytechnic Univ, Virginia Polytechnic Univ
Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: Macroevolution and macroecology
- Arlin Stoltzfus, Rutger Vos; Center for Advanced Res in Biotech, Simon Fraser Univ
Evolutionary informatics: Supporting interoperability in evolutionary analysis
- Karen Strier, Susan Alberts; Univ of Wisconsin-Madison, Duke Univ
Evolutionary ecology of primate life histories

Triangle Working Group

- Marcy Uyenoyama, Alade Tokuta, Rasmus Nielsen; Duke Univ, North Carolina Central Univ, Univ Copenhagen
Genomic patterns and processes of introgression

Year 3 - 12/1/06 - 11/30/07
Round 4 - March 2007

Postdoctoral Fellows

- Brian O'Meara, Univ of California, Davis
Methods to examine trait evolution on trees: advancing the field
- Paula Spaeth, Stanford University
Competition and meso-evolutionary change in the mammalian fossil record

Sabbatical Scholars

- Malcolm Schug, Univ of North Carolina at Greensboro
The role of crossing-over and recombination in adaptive evolution

Triangle Visiting Scholars (no NESCent funding)

- David Pfennig, Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Phenotypic plasticity and the origins of diversity
- Mark Rausher, Duke Univ
Evolutionary genetics and molecular evolution

Catalysis Group

- Daniel Hartline, David Colman, Petra Hoepcke Lenz, Mark Martindale, Elaine Seaver, Gunter Paul Wagner; Univ Hawaii, McGill Univ, Univ Hawaii, Univ Hawaii, Univ Hawaii, Yale Univ
Myelin, a new model for evolutionary innovation

Working Groups

- Lauren Buckley, Michael Angilletta, Robert Holt, Joshua Tewksbury; Santa Fe Institute, Indiana St Univ, Univ Florida, Univ Washington
Mechanistic distribution models: energetics, fitness, and population dynamics
- David Lahti and Susan A. Foster; Univ of Massachusetts, Clark Univ
Relaxed selection and trait loss in evolution
- Charles Nunn and Brian Hare; Univ of California at Berkeley, Duke Univ
How does cognition evolve?

Round 5 - September 2007

Sabbatical Scholars

- George Gilchrist, College of William & Mary
Evolution of performance curves in seasonal environments

Short-Term Scholars

- Sabine Hennequin, University Paris 6
Phylogenetic rate heterogeneity and evolution in filmy ferns (Hymenophyllaceae)
- Andrew Hipp, Alexander Platt; The Morton Arboretum, Univ of Southern California
Estimating the probability of continuous character transitions on trees

Working Groups

- Michael Schwartz, Fred Allendorf; USDA Forest Service, Univ of Montana
Genetic monitoring: Development of tools for conservation and management (w/ NCEAS)
- Samantha Forde, Ivana Gudelj; Univ of California, Santa Cruz; Univ of Bath, UK
Mathematical models, microbes & evolutionary diversification
- Diddahal Govindaraju, Andrew Clark, Trudy Mackay, Stephen Stearns; Boston Univ, Cornell Univ, North Carolina State Univ, Yale Univ
Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations
- Kenneth Kozak, Catherine Graham, Carsten Rahbek; Univ of Minnesota, Stony Brook Univ, Univ of Copenhagen
Montane diversity in space and time

Year 4: 12/1/07 - 11/30/08
Round 6 - March 2008

Postdoctoral Fellows

- Josh Auld, Univ of Pittsburgh
Evaluating the effects of inbreeding on dispersal
- Carlos Botero, Cornell Univ
Evolution of conventional signals: From individuals to populations and back
- Marc Lajeunesse, Cornell Univ
Meta-analysis and the comparative phylogenetic method
- Trina Roberts, Univ of Alaska, Fairbanks
Sticky tips and misplaced roots: Is there a bias in intraspecific phylogenetics?
- Stephen Smith, Yale Univ
Integrating species distribution modeling and phylogenetics

Sabbatical Scholars

- Michael Antolin, Colorado State Univ
Sabbatical book project: Genetics of small populations

- Stephen "Christian" d'Orgeix, Virginia State Univ
Evolution courses, mountaintop lizards and a view toward the future research
- Elizabeth Lacey, Univ of North Carolina at Greensboro
Temperature and the evolution of floral design
- Robert Pennock, Michigan State Univ
Darwinian design: From artificial life to evolving intelligence

Short-Term Scholars

- Michael Alfaro, Luke Harmon, Gene Hunt; Washington State Univ, Univ of Idaho, Smithsonian Institution
Integrating fossil and molecular data in the study of diversification
- Tal Dagan, Univ of Duesseldorf
The frequency and evolution of lateral gene transfer by DNA repair mechanisms
- Oliver Eulenstein, Iowa State Univ
Gene tree parsimony for genome-scale studies
- Jessica Gurevitch, Gordon Fox, Inderjit Singh, Max Taub, Glenda Wardle; Stony Brook Univ, Univ of South Florida, Univ of Delhi, Univ of Sydney, Southwestern Univ
Toward a general theory of biological invasions
- David Houle, Florida State Univ
Measurement theory and evolutionary rates
- Enrico Pontelli, Brandon Chisham, Francisco Prosdocimi, Arlin Stoltzfus, Julie Thompson; New Mexico State Univ, New Mexico State Univ, Univ of Strasbourg, NIST, Univ of Strasbourg
Comparative data analysis ontology (CDAO)

Triangle Visiting Scholars (no NESCent funding)

- Marcy Uyenoyama, Duke Univ
Sampling-based methods for association mapping
- Brian Wiegmann, North Carolina State Univ
Phylogenetic relationships in the order Diptera primarily from DNA sequence data

Visiting Scholars

- Robert K. Peet, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Application of taxon concepts in biodiversity informatics (not funded)

Working Groups

- Charles Fenster, Scott Armbruster, Pamela Diggle; Univ of Maryland; Univ of Alaska, Fairbanks; Univ of Colorado
Floral assembly: Quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure
- Scott Hodges, Elena Kramer, Hopi Hoekstra; Univ of California, Santa Barbara; Harvard Univ; Harvard Univ
Building tools for emerging model systems in Development, Evolution, and Ecology

Catalysis Meetings

- Christina Richards, Oliver Bosssdorf, Massimo Pigliucci; New York Univ, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Stony Brook Univ
What role, if any, does heritable epigenetic variation play in phenotypic evolution?
- Jack Sites, Daniel Faith; Brigham Young University, Australian Museum
Perspectives on the origin and conservation of biodiversity in Patagonia

Round 7 - September 2008**Working Groups**

- David Pfennig, Armin Moczek; Univ of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Indiana Univ
Evolution and development of polyphenisms: Pathways to innovation and diversification
- Christine Wall, Susan Williams, Rebecca German, Chris Vinyard; Duke Univ, Ohio Univ, Johns Hopkins Univ, Medical College of Ohio
Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

Catalysis Meetings

- Cynthia Beall, Peter Robbins; Case Western Reserve Univ, Oxford Univ
Human evolution and adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia
- Erika Edwards, Caroline Stromberg, Colin Osborne; Brown Univ, Univ of Washington, Univ of Sheffield
Toward a new synthesis of the evolutionary history and ecology of C4 grasses

Year 5: 12/1/08 - 11/30/09**Round 8 - March 2009****Postdoctoral Fellows**

- Julie Meachen-Samuels; Univ of California - Los Angeles
Competition, Guild Structure and Evolution in the Carnivora

- Benjamin Redelings; NC State Univ
Improved Probabilistic Models of Insertion/Deletion for Phylogenetic Inference
- Liam Revell; Harvard Univ
Process and pattern in the phylogenetic analysis of comparative data
- Juan Santos; Univ of Texas
Multivariate evolutionary analysis: integrating structural equation modeling and phylogenetics
- Eric Schuettpelez; Duke University
A Phylogenetic Approach to Understanding the Evolution of the Earth's Biomes
- Gregor Yanega; Univ of Connecticut
A comparative phylogenetic approach to the study of insular avian phenotypes

Sabbatical Scholars

- James H. Hunt; NC State Univ
The Evolution of Sociality
- Michael Rosenberg; Arizona State Univ, Tempe
Geography, Phylogeny, and Population: An Evolutionary Synthesis

Short-Term Scholars

- Travis Ingram; Univ of British Columbia
Divergence on multiple niche axes during adaptive radiation: An evolutionary metacommunity simulation model
- Peter Midford; Univ of Kansas
Alignment of Phenotype Ontologies

Working Groups

- Alexei Drummond, Andrew Rambaut, Marc Suchard; Univ of Auckland, Univ of Edinburgh, Univ of California-Los Angeles
Software for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis by Sampling Trees
- Margaret Hall, Christopher Heesy, Andrew Iwaniuk; Midwestern Univ, Midwestern Univ, Univ of Lethbridge
Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology
- Courtney Murren, Carl Schlichting; College of Charleston, Univ of Connecticut
Costs of Phenotypic Plasticity and Adaptation to Novel Environments
- Rebecca Safran, Albert Uy; Univ of Colorado at Boulder, Syracuse Univ
An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation

Catalysis Meetings

- David Sloan Wilson; SUNY at Binghamton
The Nature of Regulation: How Evolutionary Theory Can Inform the Regulation of Large-Scale Human Social Interactions

Round 9 - September 2009**Sabbatical Scholars**

- John Logsdon; Univ. of Iowa
Sex, cells: an evolutionary inquiry into sexual reproduction

Short-Term Scholars

- Roy Plotnick; Univ. of Illinois at Chicago
Movement Paleocology, Trace Fossils, and the Evolution of Behavior
- Lennart Olsson; Friedrich-Schiller-Universität, Erbertstr
The origin of evolutionary novelties in amphibian head development
- Frans Plooi; Arnhem- Netherlands
Translation of field notes for developmental study of chimpanzee vocal communication

Working Groups

- Kathleen Donohue, Rubio de Casas; Duke Universtiy, Duke University
Germination, Trait Coevolution, and Niche Limits in Changing Environments
- Erika J Edwards, Nicolas Salamin, Stephen A. Smith; Brown University, University of Lausanne, Duke University
Grass Phylogeny Working Group II: Inferring the complex history of C4 photosynthesis in grasses
- Norman Johnson, Louise Mead, James Smith; Univ. of Massachusetts-Amherst, National Center for Science Education, Michigan State University
Communicating the Relevance of Human Evolution

Catalysis Meetings

- Alan Jones; Univ. of North Carolina
Evolution of G Protein Coupled Signaling: Lineages, Constraints, and Tempo
- Jessica Metcalf, Robert Guralnick, Alan Cooper; Univ. of Adelaide, Univ. Colorado, Boulder, Univ. of Adelaide
Integrating datasets to investigate megafaunal extinction in the Late Quaternary